

Phytochemical investigation and *in vitro* biological screening of *Curcuma zedoaria*

V. Vinodhini^a, M. Himaja^{*a}, V. Sai Saraswathi^a, S. R. Sathish Kumar^b and V. K. Bhaskara Rao^b

^aPharmaceutical Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : drmhimaja@gmail.com

^bEnvironmental Biotechnology Division, School of Biosciences and Technology, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract : *Curcuma zedoaria* a traditionally used medicinal plant belonging to the Zingiberaceae family. Rationale of the study was to screen the extracts for the presence of various phytoconstituents and examine its antibacterial potential and its α -amylase enzyme inhibitory activity. The soxhlet extraction of *C. zedoaria* rhizomes with different solvents and phytochemical screening of the extracts showed the presence of terpenoids, saponins, phenols, and alkaloids. The extracts were screened for its antimicrobial activity. From the results, it was observed that chloroform extract (CHE) showed potent activity compared to standard drug (Chloroamphenicol), whereas the ethyl acetate (EAE) and aqueous extracts (AQE) have shown moderate inhibitory activity. The dose of 10 mg/ml of EAE significantly inhibited the α -amylase activity.

Keywords : *Curcuma zedoaria*, phytochemical investigation, α -amylase enzyme, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Curcuma zedoaria a perennial herb, belonging to the Zingiberaceae family¹, is traditionally being used for the treatment of various ailments like vomiting, menstrual hematorrhea², leucorrhoeal discharge³ and as an antiallergan⁴. The rhizomes of *Curcuma* species were traditionally used for the treatment of cut wounds and are known for its antibacterial activity. Reports showed *Curcuma zedoaria* plant to possess potent antioxidant activity^{5,6}, anti-inflammatory activity⁷, antitumor activity^{8,9} and anti-hyperlipidemic activity¹⁰. Recent studies stated that rhizomes of *Curcuma zedoaria* contained curcumin and α -pinene and possesses significant anti-hyperglycemic activity¹¹. The methanol extract of leaves and rhizomes of *Curcuma zedoaria* was found to have potent glucose tolerance level in mice, while studying its anti-hyperglycemic activity in comparison with drug glibenclamide¹².

In the present study the extracts are investigated for the presence of various phytoconstituents. The extracts screened for their potential to combat infectious organisms and were studied for efficacy in inhibiting α -amylase enzyme activity.

Experimental

Collection and processing :

The rhizome was collected from Southern part of Orissa and was authenticated by ABS botanical conservation, research and training centre, Salem. The rhizome was dried under shade and processed into fine powder using a blender and stored in air tight contained for further use.

Extraction :

The powdered plant material of 100 g sample was extracted using soxhlet method with solvents like aqueous (AQE), chloroform (CHE) and ethyl acetate (EAE). The extracts were evaporated to dryness under vacuum using rotary evaporator and stored in desiccator for further analysis. The extracts obtained are subjected to qualitative test for the identification of various phytoconstituents.

Phytochemical screening :

The phytochemical screening was performed for AQE, CHE and EAE extracts by standard procedures J. B. Harborne¹³. The qualitative screening of extracts for the presence of secondary metabolites was carried and the results are tabulated (Table 1).

Table 1. Phytochemical screening of rhizome of *Curcuma zedoaria*

Phytoconstituents	AQE	EAE	CHE
Alkaloids	+	-	+
Carbohydrates	+	-	-
Glycosides	+	-	-
Phytosteroids	-	-	-
Phenols	++	++	-
Tannins	++	-	-
Terpenoids	-	+++	+++
Saponins	+++	-	-
Flavanoids	-	-	-

(+) - Presence, (-) - absence.

*In vitro biological activities :**Antibacterial activity :*

Bacterial strains collected from microbial type culture collection (MTCC), IMTECH, Chandigarh, India. The Gram +ve *S. aureus* (MTCC 9760), *B. subtilis* (MTCC 9411) and Gram -ve *E. coli* (MTCC 1679), *K. pneumonia* (MTCC 9401) clinical strain were used. Agar well diffusion¹⁴ method was followed for determining the antibacterial property of the extracts. Extracts of 100 µg/ml concentration were added to the petri dishes previously inoculated with bacterial strain. Petri dishes are then sealed and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The zone of inhibition of bacterial growth was measured in mm and the values reported in Table 2. Standard drug Chloroamphenicol was used as reference.

Table 2. Antibacterial activity result

Entry	Gram-positive		Gram-negative	
	Zone of inhibition (mm)		Zone of inhibition (mm)	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>
Chloroamphenicol	22	18	24	27
AQE	12	15	12	10
CHE	13	17	12	30
EAE	15	11	13	20
DMSO	-	-	-	-

(-) - No inhibition zone.

Enzyme inhibitory assay :

α-Amylase enzyme inhibitory activity of the plant extracts in hydrolysis of starch was studied¹⁵ using acarbose as standard. Extracts of 10 mg/ml concentration pre-in-

cubated with α-amylase enzyme solution (5 U/ml) for 20 min. 0.5% starch solution in 20 mM phosphate buffer was added to the reaction mixture and incubated at 37 °C in addition for 20 min. The catalytic reaction was terminated by addition of 2,4-dinitro-salicylic acid (DNSA) reagent to the reaction mixture, and maintained at 100 °C for 15 min. The samples were diluted and the absorbance (Abs) was measured by spectrophotometric method at 540 nm. The percentage inhibition for the samples and control were calculated from the mean absorption.

Alpha amylase inhibition (%) =

$$\frac{\text{Abs. of control} - \text{Abs. of sample}}{\text{Abs. of control}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion*Phytochemical screening results :*

The preliminary phytochemical screening of the AQE extract showed positive for majority of the phytoconstituent and saponin was found to be major constituent present. Terpenoid was found to be the major phytoconstituents in both CHE and EAE extract.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial potential of the extracts against the bacterial strains were studied. The CHE extract was found to be more efficient against *K. pneumonia* compared to the standard drug Chloroamphenicol. The antibacterial

efficiency of CHE extract may be due to the presence of terpenoids and alkaloids present. Other extracts showed moderate activity against the Gram-positive and Gram-negative organism.

α-Amylase enzyme inhibitory assay :

Fig. 1. % Inhibition of α -amylase enzyme inhibitory.

From the *in vitro* enzyme inhibitory by DNSA method it was found that the EAE extract of 10 mg/ml concentration showed significant inhibitory activity compared to the standard. The ethyl acetate extract showed 45% enzyme inhibition against standard acarbose, may be due the presence of terpenoids and phenolic compounds. While CHE and AQE showed 40% and 38% enzyme inhibition moderated inhibitory activity. Further research is recommended in identifying the active constituents, responsible for the anti-hyperglycemic property of the crude extracts.

Conclusion

It is shown that the extracts of *C. zedoaria* possessed potent antimicrobial activity and moderate α -amylase enzyme inhibitory activity. The presence of terpenoids and phenolic compounds might play an important role in controlling the activities. Further investigation on individual phytoconstituents would lead to the identification and development of potent lead molecules.

Acknowledgement

We the authors are thankful to the VIT-SIF lab, VIT University for providing the necessary facilities to do the research work.

References

1. S. C. Bhandari and C. Vanaushaddhi, "An Encycl. Indian Botanic and Herbs", 1992, 7.
2. R. Lobo, K. S. Prabhu and A. Shirwaikor, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 2009, **101**, 249.
3. B. Nambisan, B. Wilson and Abrahamb, *J. Ethopharmacol.*, 2005, **99**, 147.
4. C. K. Khare, *Indian Med. Plants : An Illus. Dict.*, 2007, 1.
5. M. Himaja, Anand Ranjitha, M. V. Ramana, M. Anand and Asif Karigar, *Int. J. Res. Ayur. Pharmacy*, 2010, **1**, 414.
6. A. M. Abbasi and Aziz-Ur-Rehaman, *Asian J. Phar. Biol. Res.*, 2011, **1**, 525.
7. Madan, L. Kaushik and Sunil S. Jalalpure, *Asian J. Phar. Clin. Res.*, 2011, **4**, 90.
8. J. P. Fernandes, A. C. Mello-moura, M. M. Marques and M. A. Nicoletti, *Acta Odontol Scand.*, 2012, **70**, 610.
9. S. Lakshmi, G. Padmaja and P. Remani, *Int. J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, 1.
10. R. Mohammed, Md. N. Kabilul Azam, P. Sujana, Sania, R. Shahnaz and J. Rownak, *Int. J. Pharmtech. Res.*, 2012, **4**, 125.
11. M. A. El-Moselly, A. Taye, S. S. Sharkanie, S. F. El-Sisi and A. F. Ahmed, *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 2011, **49**, 1129.
12. J. Shoha, H. Jahan, A. A. Mamun, M. T. Hossain, S. Ahmed, M. M. Hosain, S. Rahman and M. Rahmatullah, *Adv. Nat. Appl. Sci.*, 2010, **5**, 6.
13. J. B. Harborne, "Phytochemical Methods", 2nd ed., Chapman and Hall, 288.
14. A. R. Srividya, Y. Ajith Kumar and S. P. Dhanbal, *Arch. Pharm. Sci. and Res.*, 2009, **1**, 14.
15. M. A. Mogale, S. L. Lebelo, N. Thovhogi, A. N. De Freitas and L. J. Shai, *Afr. J. Biotech.*, 2011, **10**, 15033.